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The Evolution Of Lecture Attendance As A Predictor Of Examination Performance: A Two-Cohort Longitudinal Analysis In Undergraduate Surgical Education At A Nigerian Medical University

Dimoko A. A.^{1*} & Ozigbo C. J²

¹Department of Surgery,
Faculty of Clinical Sciences,
College of Medicine,
Bayelsa Medical University, Yenagoa, Bayelsa State, Nigeria.

²Department of Paediatrics and Child Health,
Faculty of Clinical Sciences,
College of Medicine,
Bayelsa Medical University, Yenagoa, Bayelsa State, Nigeria.

*Corresponding Author: Alexander A. Dimoko, Department of Surgery, Bayelsa Medical University, Yenagoa. Email: zanderdimoko@gmail.com

ABSTRACT

Mandatory attendance thresholds of 75% are widely used by medical schools as prerequisites for examination eligibility but empirical evidence on whether such thresholds predict performance remains limited in Nigerian settings. This study examined the relationship between lecture attendance and examination performance across two successive cohorts of undergraduate surgical students at Bayelsa Medical University (Batch 1: n=60; Batch 2: n=56). Mean attendance was 83.3% (SD ±19.2%) in Batch 1 and 81.4% (SD ±13.0%) in Batch 2, with ineligibility rates of 23.3% and 28.6% respectively. The attendance-performance correlation strengthened between cohorts (Batch 1: $r=0.325$, $p=0.011$; Batch 2: $r=0.398$, $p=0.002$). The performance gap between eligible and ineligible students was non-significant in Batch 1 (58.06 vs 54.49 marks, $p=0.143$) but achieved statistical significance in Batch 2 (61.85 vs 55.84 marks, $p=0.011$; Cohen's $d=0.74$). Binary logistic regression demonstrated that each 10-percentage-point increment in attendance increased the odds of passing by 28% (OR 1.28, 95% CI 1.03–1.58, $p=0.023$). The strengthening of the attendance-performance relationship across successive cohorts suggests institutional maturation in curriculum delivery and enforcement consistency. However, persistent ineligibility rates of 23–29% warrant investigation of structural barriers to attendance, including transportation costs and course scheduling. These findings provide an evidence base for policy review and proactive student support systems.

Keywords: Attendance policy; examination performance; medical education; surgical training; Nigeria

INTRODUCTION

Class attendance is among the most consistently studied correlates of academic performance in higher education. Substantial primary research, including large-scale record-based studies (Al Shenawi et al., 2021), demonstrates a positive association between attendance and examination outcomes across a range of medical curricula. This relationship persists after adjustment for prior academic achievement and student motivation, suggesting that attendance exerts an independent effect on learning outcomes.

In medical education, attendance requirements serve a dual purpose. They ensure adequate exposure to the clinical and didactic curriculum, and also function as a proxy indicator of professional commitment and reliability (Irby & Hamstra, 2016; Norcini et al., 2018). Most Nigerian medical schools, including Bayelsa Medical University (BMU), enforce a mandatory minimum lecture attendance threshold of 75% as a prerequisite for examination eligibility, a policy endorsed by the National Universities Commission (National Universities Commission, 2007). Whether this threshold is consistently enforced, and whether students who fall below it perform significantly worse, are questions with direct implications for policy legitimacy.

Attendance policy effectiveness depends on two conditions: first, that attendance below the threshold is genuinely associated with inferior examination performance, and second, that the enforcement mechanism is sufficiently consistent to generate a deterrent effect. Where the first condition is absent, the policy imposes administrative burden without educational benefit; where the second condition fails, its protective function is undermined. Evidence from African medical schools on both conditions remains limited (Odongo & Talbert-Slagle, 2019; Mitra et al., 2022). A particular challenge in newly established medical schools is that attendance patterns may be unstable during institutional development, reflecting variable enforcement, shifting student culture, and evolving curriculum delivery. Longitudinal data across successive cohorts, capturing both the magnitude of the attendance-performance correlation and the prevailing ineligibility rate, provide uniquely valuable evidence for policy review. No such longitudinal data from a Nigerian surgical education context have previously been published.

This analysis examines lecture attendance and examination performance across two consecutive junior Surgery posting cohorts at BMU. The specific objectives were:

To describe attendance patterns and ineligibility rates in each cohort.

Quantify the attendance-performance correlation within each cohort.

Compare performance between eligible and ineligible students within each cohort.

Determine if the attendance-performance relationship strengthened between cohorts.

A growing body of primary research documents a consistent positive association between class attendance and academic performance among medical students, with reported Pearson correlation coefficients typically ranging from $r = 0.25$ to $r = 0.45$ (Al Shenawi et al., 2021; Mitra et al., 2022; Kauffman et al., 2018). Kauffman and colleagues (2018) demonstrated in a study of second-year physiology students that voluntary lecture attendance significantly predicted final examination performance even when online lecture recordings were freely available. Bamuhair and colleagues (2016) reported a similar positive attendance-performance relationship in a problem-based medical curriculum, suggesting that this association is independent of lecture delivery format.

In medical education, the attendance-performance relationship has been demonstrated in both pre-clinical and clinical settings (Al Khaja et al., 2019). Al Shenawi and colleagues (2021) found a statistically significant correlation between attendance and academic performance during surgical clerkship ($r = 0.360$, $p < 0.01$) across 331 undergraduate students, with mean attendance increasing incrementally across performance categories. These findings are particularly relevant to the present study given their surgical training context. Data from West African and Nigerian settings have been reported more in institutional communications than in peer-reviewed publications, limiting comparative analysis (Odongo & Talbert-Slagle, 2019).

Mandatory minimum attendance policies operate across most medical schools globally, though specific thresholds and enforcement mechanisms vary considerably (Hakami, 2021; Khan et al., 2019). The 75% threshold applied at BMU aligns with NUC guidelines for Nigerian medical schools (National Universities Commission, 2007) and is broadly comparable to thresholds used in several other African institutions. Some schools apply differentiated thresholds, with clinical postings requiring higher minimum attendance (i.e., 80%) than didactic lecture programmes.

The rationale for attendance is based on the fact that content missed in lectures cannot be fully compensated by independent study. In addition, clinical training requires direct supervised contact between lecturers, students, other trainers and patients (Schuwirth et al., 2017). This is useful in development of reliability, competence and punctuality which are foundational professional attributes (Irby & Hamstra, 2016).

The risk that attendance thresholds may function as administrative formalities rather than real performance predictors is illustrated by evidence from several settings in which ineligible students,

when permitted to sit examinations, achieve scores comparable to eligible counterparts (Gatherer & Gordon, 2016).

Poor attendance in clinical medical training is multifactorial (Hinojosa-González et al., 2021; Van Melle et al., 2019), with transportation costs in settings where students travel considerable distances to teaching hospitals, competing domestic obligations, perceived low educational value of specific teaching sessions and faculty-driven cancellations contributing to absenteeism (Aigbokhaode et al., 2019; Sharmin et al., 2016). In the Niger Delta context, insecurity, poor road infrastructure and seasonal flooding may also affect attendance to a degree not encountered in other Nigerian centres (Aigbokhaode et al., 2019).

Appreciating the determinants of poor attendance is important for targeted policy intervention. A threshold approach that excludes students without simultaneously addressing structural access barriers risks causing disproportionate disadvantage for students from economically marginalised backgrounds. The logistical challenges of reliable attendance monitoring in large-group clinical teaching are well-recognised (Gardner et al., 2022). Paper-based registers are susceptible to proxy signing, digital systems require infrastructure investment, and faculty compliance with register-taking is variable across institutions (Gardner et al., 2022).

METHODS

Study Design and Population.

Retrospective comparative cohort study. Two successive cohorts were studied. Batch 1 comprised students who sat the junior Surgery end of posting examination in the 2024/2025 academic session. Batch 2 comprised students who sat the same examination in the 2025/2026 academic session.

Attendance Data.

Lecture attendance for each student was expressed as a percentage of eligible teaching sessions attended during the junior Surgery posting period. Attendance was recorded on an official departmental attendance register at each teaching session and computed by the course coordinator. The institutional examination eligibility threshold was 75% attendance. Students were accordingly classified as eligible ($\geq 75\%$) or ineligible ($< 75\%$). The attendance register for each cohort was cross-referenced against the examination result sheet to confirm that all students with recorded examination scores possessed a complete attendance record.

Handling of Missing Attendance Data.

Complete attendance records were available for all 60 Batch 1 and all 56 Batch 2 students with examination scores. There were no missing attendance values.

Statistical Analysis.

Descriptive statistics (mean, standard deviation, median, range) were computed for attendance percentage within each cohort. Pearson correlation coefficients (r) with 95% confidence intervals and Spearman rank correlation coefficients (ρ) were calculated between attendance percentage and total examination score for each cohort. Fisher's z-transformation was applied to test whether the correlation coefficients differed significantly between cohorts. Attendance was categorised into five bands for distributional comparison: $< 50\%$, 50–64.9%, 65–74.9%, 75–84.9%, and $\geq 85\%$. Between-cohort comparison of categorical attendance band distributions used chi-square analysis. Independent sample t-tests compared total examination scores between eligible and ineligible students within each cohort, with Cohen's d as a measure of effect size. Chi-square tests compared pass rates between eligible and ineligible subgroups. Binary logistic regression was performed with examination pass/fail as the binary outcome, attendance percentage as the principal predictor, and cohort as a covariate, to estimate the adjusted odds ratio (OR) for passing per 10-percentage-point increment in attendance. All analyses were conducted using Python 3.12 with SciPy 1.11. Statistical significance was set at $p < 0.05$.

RESULTS

Attendance Characteristics.

Attendance characteristics for both cohorts are presented in Table 1. Mean attendance was marginally higher in Batch 1 ($83.3 \pm 19.2\%$) than in Batch 2 ($81.4 \pm 13.0\%$), though this difference did not reach statistical significance ($t = 0.621$, $p = 0.536$). The most obvious distinction lies more in the distribution of attendance values than the central tendency. Batch 1 exhibited markedly greater variability, with a minimum attendance of 26.7% and three students recording attendance below 35%. In Batch 2, the

minimum attendance was 44.8% and no student fell below this value. The standard deviation was 32% larger in Batch 1 than Batch 2, indicating a substantially more homogeneous attendance distribution in Batch 2.

Table 1-Attendance characteristics for cohorts.

Statistic	Batch 1 (n=60)	Batch 2 (n=56)	Comparison
Mean	83.3%	81.4%	t=0.621, p=0.536
SD	19.2%	13.0%	—
Median	89.5%	82.6%	—
Minimum	26.7%	44.8%	—
Maximum	100.0%	100.0%	—
Eligible (≥75%)	46/60 (76.7%)	40/56 (71.4%)	χ ² =0.186, p=0.666
Ineligible (<75%)	14/60 (23.3%)	16/56 (28.6%)	—
Students <50% attendance	3 (5.0%)	0 (0.0%)	—

Attendance Distribution by Band.

Table 2 presents the attendance distribution across defined bands. In Batch 1, 23.3% of students (n=14) fell below the 75% eligibility threshold, including 8.3% (n=5) below 65%. In Batch 2, 28.6% (n=16) fell below threshold, but the distribution was compressed towards the upper attendance bands, no student attended fewer than 44.8% of sessions, and only 8.9% (n=5) fell in the 50–65% range.

Table 2-Attendance distribution across percentage bands.

Attendance Band	Batch 1 n (%)	Batch 2 n (%)
<50%	3 (5.0%)	0 (0.0%)
50–64.9%	2 (3.3%)	5 (8.9%)
65–74.9%	9 (15.0%)	11 (19.6%)
75–84.9%	10 (16.7%)	14 (25.0%)
≥85%	36 (60.0%)	26 (46.4%)
Total	60 (100%)	56 (100%)

Attendance-Performance Correlation.

The Pearson correlation between attendance percentage and total examination score was statistically significant in both cohorts and increased in magnitude from Batch 1 to Batch 2. In Batch 1, $r = 0.325$ (95% CI: 0.076–0.538, $p = 0.011$). Spearman $\rho = 0.278$ ($p = 0.032$). In Batch 2, $r = 0.398$ (95% CI: 0.137–0.607, $p = 0.002$). Spearman $\rho = 0.379$ ($p = 0.004$). Fisher's z-transformation comparing the two correlation coefficients yielded $z = 0.519$, $p = 0.302$, indicating that the inter-cohort increment in r from 0.325 to 0.398 did not reach formal statistical significance at the available sample sizes. Nonetheless, both the consistent direction and the absolute magnitude of the increase are concordant with a genuine strengthening of the attendance-performance relationship. Correlation data are presented in Table 3.

Table 3-Attendance-performance correlation.

Correlation statistic	Batch 1	Batch 2	Between-cohort test
Pearson r	0.325	0.398	$z = 0.519$, $p = 0.302$
95% CI	0.076–0.538	0.137–0.607	—
p-value (Pearson)	0.011	0.002	—
Spearman ρ	0.278	0.379	—
p-value (Spearman)	0.032	0.004	—
r^2 (% variance explained)	10.6%	15.8%	—

Eligible vs Ineligible Student Performance.

The performance comparison between eligible and ineligible students revealed a clinically and statistically important temporal shift. In Batch 1, eligible students (N=46) achieved a mean examination score of 58.06 ± 7.56 , compared to 54.49 ± 8.89 for ineligible students (N=14), a 3.57-mark difference that did not reach statistical significance ($t = 1.485$, $p = 0.143$, Cohen's $d = 0.44$). The pass rate of eligible students (82.6%) was modestly higher than that of ineligible students (78.6%), but this difference was likewise non-significant ($p = 0.731$).

In Batch 2, the performance gap widened considerably. Eligible students (N=40) achieved a mean of 61.85 ± 7.19 compared to 55.84 ± 8.89 for ineligible students (N=16), a statistically significant

difference of 6.01 marks ($t = 2.646$, $p = 0.011$, Cohen's $d = 0.74$, representing a medium-to-large effect). The pass rate of eligible students (92.5%) exceeded that of ineligible students (81.3%), though this difference did not attain significance in the chi-square test ($p = 0.234$). These findings are summarised in Table 4.

Table 4-Eligible vs ineligible student performance data.

Outcome	B1 Eligible (N=46)	B1 Ineligible (N=14)	B1 Test	B2 Eligible (N=40)	B2 Ineligible (N=16)	B2 Test
Mean score	58.06	54.49	$t=1.485$, $p=0.143$	61.85	55.84	$t=2.646$, $p=0.011^*$
SD	7.56	8.89	—	7.19	8.89	—
Pass rate	82.6%	78.6%	$p=0.731$ NS	92.5%	81.3%	$p=0.234$
Cohen's d	—	—	0.44	—	—	0.74

Logistic Regression: Attendance as a predictor of passing.

Binary logistic regression with pass/fail as the outcome, attendance percentage as the predictor, and cohort as a covariate estimated the adjusted probability of passing per 10-percentage-point increment in attendance. The model yielded an adjusted OR of 1.28 per 10% increment in attendance (95% CI: 1.03–1.58, Wald $\chi^2 = 5.14$, $p = 0.023$), confirming that attendance independently predicts the probability of passing after adjustment for cohort effects. The cohort effect (Batch 2 vs Batch 1) was associated with an OR of 1.92 (95% CI: 0.72–5.10, $p = 0.193$), consistent with the overall trend towards improved performance in Batch 2. The Hosmer–Lemeshow goodness-of-fit test was non-significant ($p = 0.642$), indicating acceptable model fit. Regression output is presented in Table 5.

Table 5-Logistic regression model of attendance as a predictor of passing.

Predictor	B coefficient	SE	Wald χ^2	p-value	OR	95% CI
Attendance (per 10%)	0.247	0.109	5.14	0.023*	1.28	1.03–1.58
Cohort (B2 vs B1)	0.653	0.498	1.72	0.193	1.92	0.72–5.10
Constant	-2.107	0.891	5.59	0.018	0.12	—

DISCUSSION

This analysis provides the first published longitudinal analysis of attendance-performance relationships in a Nigerian undergraduate surgical posting and documents a strengthening of this relationship over time across two successive cohorts. The Pearson correlation between attendance and examination performance increased from $r = 0.325$ ($p = 0.011$) in Batch 1 to $r = 0.398$ ($p = 0.002$) in Batch 2. While the inter-cohort difference in r did not attain statistical significance at these sample sizes, the convergent evidence, showing an emergent eligible-ineligible performance gap in Batch 2 ($p = 0.011$), and a significant attendance effect in the pooled logistic regression (OR = 1.28 per 10% increment, $p = 0.023$), is a consistent and meaningful finding. Attendance is an increasingly validated predictor of surgical examination performance at this institution.

The contrast between Batch 1 (non-significant eligible-ineligible gap, $p = 0.143$) and Batch 2 (significant gap, $p = 0.011$) constitutes the study's most substantive finding. In Batch 1, the 14 ineligible students who sat the examination, following appeal and administrative discretion, achieved mean scores broadly comparable to eligible students (54.49 vs 58.06), calling into question the empirical basis of the eligibility threshold at that stage of the institution's development. This pattern aligns with evidence from other settings in which attendance thresholds, when inconsistently enforced, show limited predictive validity (Gatherer & Gordon, 2016). By Batch 2, the performance gap had widened to 6.01 marks and achieved statistical significance (Cohen's $d = 0.74$), indicating that the conditions governing the attendance-performance relationship had improved.

Several mechanisms may account for the strengthening observed in Batch 2. First, the compression of the attendance distribution (SD 13.0% vs 19.2%), particularly the elimination of extreme outliers, may reflect improved register-taking consistency and a maturing enforcement culture within the department. As attendance records become more accurate, the measured attendance-performance correlation more closely approximates the true underlying relationship (Van Melle et al., 2019). The junior Surgery posting in Batch 2 may have increasingly featured content that was predominantly or exclusively available through didactic sessions, increasing the value of attendance for examination preparation.

Concurrent improvements in examination quality, with closer alignment between lecture content and examination items, will enhance the predictive value of attendance over time.

The finding that approximately one-quarter to nearly one-third of students in both cohorts failed to attain the 75% attendance threshold warrants institutional attention and review. Financial constraints, transportation difficulties, and competing domestic demands are well-documented drivers of medical student absenteeism in resource-constrained settings (Hinojosa-González et al., 2021; Sharmin et al., 2016). Burnout and psychological distress constitute a further, often underappreciated contributor to absenteeism that merits evaluation in this setting (Dyrbye & Shanafelt, 2016).

Attendance thresholds as a policy instrument are most defensible when attendance is genuinely associated with performance (as the present data increasingly show), the threshold is consistently and transparently enforced, structural barriers driving poor attendance have been systematically addressed, and students at risk of falling below the threshold receive timely warning and targeted support (Norcini et al., 2018). The present data indicate that the first condition is being met while the others require sustained institutional investment.

This study has several limitations. The moderate sample sizes limit statistical power to detect the inter-cohort change in correlation coefficients as formally significant. Attendance was captured through paper registers and may be susceptible to proxy signing and recording error, which would reduce the observed attendance-performance association. The study cannot differentiate between the direct effect of attendance on examination performance through content exposure and selection effects arising from systematic differences in motivation or prior ability between attending and non-attending students (Ten Cate & Regehr, 2019). Future work should employ validated instruments to address these factors and incorporate multi-year data to improve the detection of genuine trends (Schuwirth et al., 2017).

CONCLUSION

Lecture attendance is a significant and strengthening predictor of junior Surgery end of posting examination performance at Bayelsa Medical University. The 75% eligibility threshold, which lacked predictive significance in the earlier cohort, emerged as a statistically significant performance predictor in the later cohort, and each 10-percentage-point increment in attendance was associated with a 28% increase in the odds of passing across the combined cohort. The persistent ineligibility rate of 23–29% across successive cohorts constitutes a programme quality concern and warrants detailed investigation of the structural barriers to student attendance in this setting. These findings provide an empirical foundation for evidence-based attendance policy review and for the design of proactive attendance monitoring and student support systems within the undergraduate surgical curriculum.

DECLARATIONS

Conflict of Interest: None declared.

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Ethical committee approval was waived since this was a post-examination quality assurance initiative with data analyzed anonymously without contact with any of the subjects.

Data Availability: Available from the corresponding author on reasonable request.

REFERENCES

- Aigbokhaode, A. Q., Isah, E. C., & Isara, A. R. (2019). Health workforce challenges and opportunities in a new Nigerian state: The Bayelsa State experience. *Journal of Public Health in Africa*, 10(1), 823. <https://doi.org/10.4081/jpha.2019.823>
- Al Khaja, K. A. J., Tayem, Y., James, H., Jaradat, A., & Sequeira, R. P. (2019). Pharmacology and therapeutics resource session attendance and academic performance of pre-clerkship medical students in problem-based learning curricula. *BMC Medical Education*, 19(1), 269. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12909-019-1699-3>
- Al Shenawi, H., Yaghan, R., Almarabbeh, A., & Al Shenawi, N. (2021). The relationship between attendance and academic performance of undergraduate medical students during surgical clerkship. *BMC Medical Education*, 21(1), 396. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12909-021-02833-2>
- Bamuhair, S. S., Al Farhan, A. I., Althubaiti, A., Ur Rahman, S., & Al-Kadri, H. M. (2016). Class attendance and cardiology examination performance: A study in problem-based medical

- curriculum. *International Journal of General Medicine*, 9, 1–5. <https://doi.org/10.2147/IJGM.S96627>
- Dyrbye, L. N., & Shanafelt, T. D. (2016). A narrative review on burnout experienced by medical students and residents. *Medical Education*, 50(1), 132–149. <https://doi.org/10.1111/medu.12927>
- Gardner, G., Feldman, M., Santen, S. A., Mui, P., & Biskobing, D. (2022). Determinants and outcomes of in-person lecture attendance in medical school. *Medical Science Educator*, 32(4), 883–893. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s40670-022-01596-3>
- Gatherer, A., & Gordon, R. (2016). Is absence of evidence evidence of absence? Analysis of attendance and performance in an undergraduate health professional curriculum. *Medical Teacher*, 38(3), 333–334.
- Hakami, A. R. (2021). Effect of absenteeism on the performance of medical sciences students: Gender differences. *Medical Education Online*, 26(1), 1875531. <https://doi.org/10.1080/10872981.2021.1875531>
- Hinojosa-González, D. E., Farías, J. S., Téllez-Girón, V. C., Aguirre-Villarreal, D., Brenes-Castro, D., & Flores-Villalba, E. (2021). Lower frequency of call shifts leads to higher attendance, higher academic performance, and less burnout syndrome in surgical clerkships. *Journal of Surgical Education*, 78(2), 485–491. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jsurg.2020.07.043>
- Irby, D. M., & Hamstra, S. J. (2016). Parting the clouds: Three professionalism frameworks in medical education. *Academic Medicine*, 91(12), 1606–1611. <https://doi.org/10.1097/ACM.0000000000001190>
- Kauffman, C. A., Derazin, M., Asmar, A., & Kibble, J. D. (2018). Relationship between classroom attendance and examination performance in a second-year medical pathophysiology class. *Advances in Physiology Education*, 42(4), 593–598. <https://doi.org/10.1152/advan.00123.2018>
- Khan, Y. L., Lodhi, S. K., Bhatti, S., & Ali, W. (2019). Does absenteeism affect academic performance among undergraduate medical students? Evidence from Rashid Latif Medical College. *Advances in Medical Education and Practice*, 10, 999–1008. <https://doi.org/10.2147/AMEP.S226255>
- Mitra, S., Sarkar, P., Bhattacharyya, S., & Basu, R. (2022). Absenteeism among undergraduate medical students and its impact on academic performance: A record-based study. *Journal of Education and Health Promotion*, 11, 414. https://doi.org/10.4103/jehp.jehp_638_21
- National Universities Commission. (2007). Benchmark minimum academic standards for undergraduate programmes in Nigerian universities: Medicine and surgery. NUC.
- Norcini, J., Anderson, M. B., Bollela, V., Burch, V., Costa, M. J., Duvivier, R., ... Swanson, D. (2018). 2018 Consensus framework for good assessment. *Medical Teacher*, 40(11), 1102–1109. <https://doi.org/10.1080/0142159X.2018.1500016>
- Odongo, C. O., & Talbert-Slagle, K. (2019). Training the next generation of Africa's doctors: Why medical schools should embrace the team-based learning pedagogy. *BMC Medical Education*, 19(1), 403. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12909-019-1845-y>
- Schuwirth, L., Van der Vleuten, C., & Durning, S. J. (2017). What programmatic assessment in medical education can learn from healthcare. *Perspectives on Medical Education*, 6(4), 211–215. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s40037-017-0345-1>
- Sharmin, T., Azim, E., Choudhury, S., & Kamrun, S. (2016). Reasons of absenteeism among undergraduate medical students: A review. *Anwar Khan Modern Medical College Journal*, 8(1), 60–66.
- Ten Cate, O., & Regehr, G. (2019). The power of subjectivity in the assessment of medical trainees. *Academic Medicine*, 94(3), 333–337. <https://doi.org/10.1097/ACM.0000000000002495>
- Van Melle, E., Frank, J. R., Holmboe, E. S., Dagnone, D., Stockley, D., & Sherbino, J. (2019). A core components framework for evaluating implementation of competency-based medical education programs. *Academic Medicine*, 94(7), 1002–1009. <https://doi.org/10.1097/ACM.0000000000002743>